

Amiel Gross is [the Head of Legal at the Center for Breakthrough Medicines](#), Philadelphia. The Center for Breakthrough Medicines is a global drug discovery and development company that specializes in identifying and developing drugs to combat major unmet medical needs. Amiel's legal expertise ensures that company policies and business strategies are aligned with legal implications and obligations.

Importance of the legal manager profile

[Amiel Gross](#) shares that the legal manager is already considered the cornerstone of modern organizations. This is because, for example, the internet has enabled a rapid international expansion of many companies and a very easy ability to collect personal data from their customers.

According to Amiel Gross, both situations, although they create great business advantages, also generate a context of high legal risk with many more "fronts to cover" compared to traditional companies.

[Highly experienced attorney](#) Amiel Gross shares that laws of data protection, content distribution, copyright applied to multiple digital formats, control of e-commerce transactions, sending and receiving money online, among others, are quite critical areas that companies must address immediately. , and the best way to do it is through a legal manager specialized in the sector of each particular business.